

Rac-5g

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xl-3-91-rac-10%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	72	Acq. Method Set:	10%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xl 3 91 rac
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	272.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 272.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	4/20/2022 11:37:19 AM CST		
Date Processed:	4/20/2022 3:38:19 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.165	393054	51.13	27851
2	9.419	375660	48.87	22906

Asy-5g

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xl-3-91-ASY-10%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	26	Acq. Method Set:	10%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 3 91 ASY
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	272.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 272.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/12/2022 4:10:26 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/20/2022 11:16:51 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.453	108750	3.69	7734
2	9.765	2836021	96.31	167037